

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL AND X-RAY STRUCTURAL INVESTIGATION OF ALLOYS OF THE As_2S_3 - TlInTe_2 SYSTEM

Ahmedova C.

*Ph.D., Associate Professor, Adiyaman University, Faculty of Arts and Sciences,
Department of Chemistry, Turkey
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6912603>*

Abstract

Chemical interactions in the As_2S_3 - TlInTe_2 system were studied by the methods of physicochemical analysis (DTA, MSA, XPA), as well as the determination of microhardness and density, and a state diagram was constructed. It has been established that the As_2S_3 - TlInTe_2 system is a quasi-binary section of the As_2S_3 - TlTe - InTe quasi-ternary system and belongs to the eutectic type. Solid solutions based on As_2S_3 are formed in the system at room temperature, reaching up to 1.5 mol. %, and on the basis of the TlInTe_2 compound up to -7 mol. %. In the As_2S_3 - TlInTe_2 system, under normal cooling conditions, extensive areas of glass formation are obtained. The temperature dependences of the electrophysical properties of solid solution alloys $(\text{TlInTe}_2)_{1-x}(\text{As}_2\text{S}_3)_x$ ($x=0.02; 0.03; 0.05$) have been studied.

Keywords: quasi-binary, eutectic, incongruent, system, microhardness, syngony.

INTRODUCTION

As a result of a review of the literature, it was established that ternary systems consisting of arsenic and thallium chalcogenides have been sufficiently studied [1–4], and a number of works have been studied in the field of quaternary systems [5–8]. Thallium chalcogenides, like arsenic chalcogenides, are prone to vitrification; under normal conditions, they are obtained in a glassy state.

Arsenic chalcogenides and alloys based on them have optical [9–13], photoelectric [14–18], and luminescent [19, 20] properties. In recent years, the attention of researchers has been attracted to chalcogenide glass fibers based on As_2S_3 and As_2Se_3 , which are used to transmit light in the mid-IR range and have found application in various semiconductor industries [21–25].

Currently, research is being carried out in the field of obtaining materials with functional properties that can meet the requirements of constantly developing microelectronics and computer technology, and the search for safer energy sources. The search for highly efficient optically sensitive and thermoelectric materials is an urgent task of research in this area. The preparation of materials with the participation of indium and thallium chalcogenides of complex phases based on them is also of theoretical and practical importance [26,27].

The purpose of this work is to study some of the physicochemical properties of the obtained phases with the construction of a state diagram of the As_2S_3 - TlInTe_2 system.

As_2S_3 melts with an open maximum at 310°C and crystallizes in a monoclinic system with lattice parameters: $a=11.49$; $b=9.59$; $c=4.25$ Å, $\beta=90^\circ 27'$ (sp. gr. P2/n) [28]. Density and microhardness of crystalline As_2S_3 are equal to 3.46 g/cm³ and 660 MPa, respectively, and glassy As_2S_3 density is 3.20 g/cm³, microhardness is 1300 MPa [28].

The TlInTe_2 compound melts congruently at 772°C and crystallizes in the tetragonal system with lattice parameters: $a = 8.482$ Å, $c = 7.192$ Å, density $\rho = 7.27$ g/cm³, microhardness $H\mu = 1000$ MPa [29].

EXPERIMENTAL PART

For the synthesis of alloys of the As_2S_3 - TlInTe_2 system, the primary components As_2S_3 and TlInTe_2 were first synthesized, and then the alloys of the system were synthesized directly by the ampoule method. Synthesis was first carried out in the temperature range of 500–900°C, then the temperature was lowered to 400°C and kept at this temperature for 200 h. Physical and chemical studies of alloys of the As_2S_3 - TlInTe_2 system were carried out both in the glassy and in the crystallized state by the methods of differential thermal (DTA), microstructural (MSA), X-ray phase (XRD) analysis, as well as measurements of microhardness and density.

The differential thermal analysis of the alloys of the system was carried out on a TERMOSCAN-2 device with a heating rate of 5 deg/min.

X-ray phase analysis was performed on a D2 PHASER X-ray instrument using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation with a Ni filter. The MSA alloys of the system were examined using a MIM-8 metallographic microscope. When studying the microstructure of the alloys, an etchant of the composition 10 ml NaOH + 10 ml $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 = 1:1$ was used, the etching time was 15–20 s. The microhardness of the alloys of the system was measured on a PMT-3 microhardness tester at a load of 0.10 N. The density of the alloys of the system was determined by the pycnometric method; toluene was used as the working fluid. The electrical conductivity was measured by the usual compensation method. The samples used had the shape of a parallelepiped. The experimental error was 2.7–3.0 % [30].

RESULTS AND ITS DISCUSSION

Alloys of the As_2S_3 - $TlInTe_2$ system are compact; with an increase in the content of $TlInTe_2$, their color changes from red to dark gray. Alloys of the As_2S_3 - $TlInTe_2$ system are resistant to water and air. They dissolve well in mineral acids (HNO_3 , H_2SO_4) in alkalis ($NaOH$, KOH).

As a result of the study of differential thermal analysis, it was found that on the thermograms of the alloys of the system As_2S_3 - $TlInTe_2$ in the concentration range of 0-30 mol % $TlInTe_2$, there are softening temperatures T_g 170-190°C, typical for glassy samples.

Fig.1. Microstructures of alloys of the As_2S_3 - $TlInTe_2$ system. a)-10 mol % $TlInTe_2$, б)-40 mol % $TlInTe_2$, в) 95 mol % $TlInTe_2$.

Microstructural analysis of these alloys 0-20 mol % $TlInTe_2$ showed that one cloudy phase is visible on the microstructure of the sample. Within 20-30 mol % $TlInTe_2$, crystalline inclusions gradually appear in the microstructure. On fig. 1 a, b, c show the microstructures of alloys of the As_2S_3 - $TlInTe_2$ system from different regions. On fig. 1a shows the microstructure of a

glass alloy with a content of 10 mol % $TlInTe_2$, b)-microstructures of two-phase, c) - microstructures of a solid solution alloy based on the $TlInTe_2$ compound. To confirm the results of DTA, MSA, alloys of the As_2S_3 - $TlInTe_2$ system, we carried out X-ray phase analysis containing 10, 20 30 mol % $TlInTe_2$ (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Diffractograms of alloys of the As_2S_3 - $TlInTe_2$ system. 1-10 mol %, 2-20 mol %, 3-30 mol %, $TlInTe_2$.

As can be seen from fig. 2, on diffraction patterns of alloys containing 10, 20 mol % $TlInTe_2$ has no diffraction maximum. These alloys are glassy. On the diffraction pattern of the alloy 30 mol % $TlInTe_2$, a diffraction maximum appears that this alloy is glass-ceramic. And so, X-ray phase analysis fully confirms the results of differential thermal and microstructural analyses.

According to the results of physicochemical analysis, the T-x phase diagram of the As_2S_3 - $TlInTe_2$ system was constructed (Fig. 2). It has been established

that the state diagram of the system is quasi-binary, of the eutectic type. In terms of interaction patterns, the As_2S_3 - $TlInTe_2$ systems are identical to the As_2S_3 - $TlInSe_2$ systems [31]. In the system at room temperature, solid solutions based on As_2S_3 reach 1.5 mol %, and based on $TlInTe_2$ up to -7 mol %. Under normal conditions, glass formation based on As_2S_3 extends up to 20 mol % $TlInTe_2$, and the glass-ceramic region reaches from 20 mol % $TlInTe_2$ up to 30 mol % $TlInTe_2$.

The liquidus of the As_2S_3 - TlInTe_2 system consists of monovariant curves of α -solid solutions based on As_2S_3 and β -solid solutions based on TlInTe_2 . In the concentration range of 0-15 mol % TlInTe_2 , the α -phase is released from the liquid. In the system, the α -phase and β -phase form a eutectic with a composition of 15 mol % TlInTe_2 and a temperature of 260°C . Below the solidus line, two-phase alloys ($\alpha + \beta$) crystallize. As can

be seen from Table 1, in the As_2S_3 - TlInTe_2 system, softening temperatures (T_g), density and microhardness of alloys of the As_2S_3 - TlInTe_2 system increase depending on the composition. Alloys in the range of 0-20 % TlInTe_2 - glass, and alloys with a composition of 20-30 mol % TlInTe_2 belongs to the glass-ceramic region. After prolonged annealing at 200°C for 400 h, the softening temperature T_g disappears (170 – 190°C), and the solidus and liquidus temperatures remain (Table 2).

Tab.1.

Composition of alloys of the As_2S_3 - TlInTe_2 system, DTA, results of measurements of density and microhardness before annealing

Composition, mol %		Thermal effects, K	Density, g/cm^3	Microhardness, MPa	
As_2S_3	TlInTe_2			α	β
100	0,0	170,310	3,20	1300	–
95	5,0	175,260,310	3,40	1350	–
90	10	180,260,305	3,61	1420	–
85	15	180,260	3,82	1420	–
80	20	185,260,340	4,03	1420	–
70	30	190, 260,445	4,42	–	1040

Composition of alloys of the As_2S_3 - $TlInTe_2$ system, DTA, results of measurements of density and microhardness before annealing

Composition, mol %		Thermal effects, K	Density, g/cm^3	Microhardness, MPa	
As_2S_3	$TlInTe_2$			α	β
				P=0,10 H	
100	0,0	310	3,46	740	–
95	5,0	260,310	3,55	770	–
90	10	260,305	3,84	810	–
85	15	260	4,03	840	–
80	20	260,340	4,22	Эвтек.	Эвтек.
70	30	260,445	4,30	–	–
60	40	260,525	4,97	–	1030
50	50	260,590	5,38	–	1040
40	60	260,640	5,74	–	1050
30	70	260,670	6,13	–	1050
20	80	260,715	6,51	–	1050
10	90	260,750	6,90	–	1050
5,0	95	500,760	7,30	–	1050
0,0	100	772	7,27	–	1000

The microhardness of alloys of the As_2S_3 - $TlInTe_2$ system has been studied both in glass and in crystalline form. Values of microhardness of alloys from the area of 0-30 mol % $TlInTe_2$ glasses are within (1300-1420) MPa (Table 1). After crystallization of the same areas, the microhardness changes within (740-840) MPa (Table 2). The value of microhardness (1000-1050) MPa corresponds to the microhardness of β -solid solutions

based on $TlInTe_2$. It has been established that the microhardness of glassy alloys is higher than that of crystalline alloys. These results are in good agreement with the literature data.

The temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity of the $(TlInTe_2)_{1-x}(As_2S_3)_x$ ($x=0.02; 0.03; 0.05$) solid solution was studied in the temperature range 290-500 K (Fig. 4). The samples used had the shape of a parallelepiped.

Fig.4. Temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity of solid solutions $(TlInTe_2)_{1-x}(As_2S_3)_x$ ($x=0.02; 0.03; 0.05$). 1-2 mol %, 2-3 mol %, 3-5 mol % As_2S_3 .

As can be seen from fig. 4, the curves of the temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity show that alloys of solid solutions based on TlInTe_2 in the temperature range of 290–500 K have a semiconductor character of conductivity.

With increasing temperature, the electrical conductivity of the alloys increases. With the introduction of TlInTe_2 into the composition, high resistances of compositions of 2, 3, and 5 mol % As_2S_3 , the electrical conductivity of the composition gradually decreases.

Conclusion

The nature of the chemical interaction and glass formation in the As_2S_3 - TlInTe_2 system was studied by a complex method of physicochemical analysis: differential thermal, X-ray phase, microstructural, as well as the determination of density and microhardness, a state diagram was constructed. It is established that the state diagram of the system is quasi-binary of the eutectic type. In the system at room temperature, solid solutions based on As_2S_3 reach up to 1.5 mol %, and those based on TlInTe_2 up to -7 mol %. The α -phase and β -phase form a eutectic between themselves, the composition of which corresponds to 15 mol % TlInTe_2 and melts at 260°C. Under normal conditions, glass formation based on As_2S_3 continues up to 20 mol % TlInTe_2 . For solid solutions $(\text{TlInTe}_2)_{1-x}(\text{As}_2\text{S}_3)_x$ ($x=0.02$; 0.03; 0.05) the temperature dependence of electrical conductivity was studied.

References:

1. Nazarova T.F., Kolomiets B.T. Hall effect in glassy semiconductors in the Tl_2Se , $\text{As}_2(\text{Se},\text{Te})_3$ system // *FTT*. 1960. V. 2. № 2. P. 395-392.
2. Andriegi A.M., Kolomiets B.T. Local levels in glassy Tl_2Se , As_2Te_3 // *FTT*. 1963. V. 5. № 5. P. 1461-1463.
3. Dembovsky S.A., Kirilenko V.V., Khvorostenko A.S. As_2Se_3 - Tl_2Se system // *Journal of Inorganic Chemistry*. 1969. V. 14. № 9. P. 2561-2564.
4. Dembovsky S.A., Chernov A.P., Vinogradova G.Z. Investigation of the structure of glasses by viscometry methods, the velocity of distribution of ultrasound and the study of phase diagrams in the systems As_2X_3 - AsX_3 and As_2X_3 - Tl_2X ($X=\text{S}, \text{Se}$) // In: *Glassy state*. L.: Nauka. 1971. P. 279-284.
5. Aliyev I.I., Ahmedova C.A., Rzaev R.M., Gashimov Kh.M. Phase formation in the As_2Se_3 - Tl_2S_3 system and the physico-chemical properties of the obtained phases // *Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science No 83/2022*. P 11-15.
6. Aliyev I.I., Ragimova V.M., Rizaev R.M., Gashimov Kh.M., Shakhbazov M.G., Tagiev S.I. Synthesis and investigation of phase formation and glass formation in the As_2S_3 - Tl_2Se_3 system // *Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science No 80/2022*. P.3-9.
7. Aliev I.I., Gamidova Sh.A., Suleymanova M.G., Kakhramanov Sh.T., Akhmedova J.A. The nature of chemical interaction and glass formation in the As_2Se_3 - TlS system // *Scientific journal. Archivist*. 2022. T: 7. No: 9(63). P.18-22.
8. Aliev I.I., Bagieva M.R., Babanly M.B., Aliev I.G., Veliyev J.A. Phase equilibria and glass formation

along the As_2S_3 - $\text{TlAs}_2\text{S}_2\text{Se}_2$ section of the As_2S_3 - As_2Se_3 - TlS system // *Journal of Inorganic Chemistry*. 2011.V.56. No.3. P. 498-501.

9. Burdiyan I.I., Feshchenko I.S. Photocurrent and Optical Transmission Spectra of Sn- and Pb-Doped $(\text{As}_2\text{S}_3)_{0.3}(\text{As}_2\text{Se}_3)_{0.7}$ Glass Films, *Inorgan. Materials*. 2005. V.41. № 9. P. 1013-1016.

10. Churbanov M.F., Shiryaev V.S., Skripachev I.V., Snopatin G.E., Pimenov V.G., Smetanin S.V., Shaposhnikov R.M., Fadin I.E., Pyrkov Yu.N., and Plotnichenko V.G. Vysokochistyye Kak $\text{As}_2\text{S}_{1.5}\text{Se}_{1.5}$ stekla opticheskikh volokon // *Neorgan. materials*. 2002. T.39. №2. R. 193-197.

11. Dinesh Chandra SATI, Rajendra KUMAR, Ram Mohan MEHRA Influence of Thickness Oil Optical Properties of a: As_2Se_3 Thin Films // *Turk J Phys*. 2006. V.30. P. 519- 527.

12. Hari P., Cheneya C., Luepkea G., Singha S., Tolka N., Sanghera J.S., Aggarwal D. Wavelength selective materials modification of bulk As_2S_3 and As_2Se_3 by free electron laser irradiation // *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids*. 2000. V. 270. P. 265-268.

13. Lovu M., Shutov S., Rebeja S., Colomeyco E., Popescu M. Effect of metal additives on photodarkening kinetics in amorphous As_2Se_3 films // *Journal of Optoelectronics and Advanced Materials* 2000. V. 2. Issue: 1. P. 53-58.

14. Jun J. Li Drabold. D. A.. Atomistic comparison between stoichiometric and nonstoichiometric glasses: The cases of As_2Se_3 and As_4Se_4 // *Phys. Rev*. 2001. V. 64. P. 104206-104213.

15. Hineva T., Petkova T., Popov C., Pektov P., Reithmaier J. P., Funrmann-Lieker T., Axente E., Sima F., Mihailescu C. N., Socol G., Mihailescu I. N. Optical study of thin $(\text{As}_2\text{Se}_3)_{1-x}(\text{AgI})_x$ films // *Journal of optoelectronics and Advanced Materials*. 2007. V.9. No. 2. February. P. 326-329.

16. Seema Kandpal, Kushwaha R. P. S.. Photoacoustic spectroscopy of thin films of As_2S_3 , As_2Se_3 and GeSe_2 // *Indian Academy of Sciences. PRAM ANA journal of physics*. 2007. V. 69. No. 3. P. 481-484.

17. Shiryaev V.S., Smetanin S.V., Ovchinnikov D.K., Churbanov M.F., Kryukova E.B., and Plotnichenko V.G. Effects of Oxygen and Carbon Impurities on the Optical Transmission of As_2Se_3 Glass// *Heорган. материалы*. 2005. T.41. №3. P. 308-312.

18. Aliyev I.I., Babanly M.B., Farzaliev A.A. Optical and photoelectric properties of thin films of glass $(\text{As}_2\text{Se}_3)_{1-x}(\text{TlSe})_x$ ($X=0.05-0.01$) // *XI International Conf. on physics and technology of thin films*. Ivano-Frankivsk. Ukraine May 7-12, 2007. P.86.

19. Babaev A.A., Muradov R., Sultanov S.B., Askhabov A.M. Influence of preparation conditions on the optical and photoluminescent properties of glassy As_2S_3 // *Inorg. materials*. 2008. V. 44. No.11. P. 1187-1201.

20. Kurganova A., Snopatin G.E., Suchkov A.I. X-ray fluorescence Determination of macroscopic composition of As-S, As-Se and As-S-Se glasses // *Inorg. materials*. 2009. V.45. No. 12. S. 1408-1413.

21. Diez A., Birks T.A., Reeves W.H., Mangan B.J., and Russell P.St.J., Excitation of cladding modes in photonic crystal fibers by flexural acoustic waves //

Optics Lett. 2000. V.25. P. 1499-1501.

22. Fu L.B., Fuerbach A., Littler I.C.M., Eggleton B.J., Efficient optical pulse compression using Chalcogenide single-mode fibers // Appl. Phys. Lett. 2006. V.88. P. 081116.

23. Fu L.B., Rochette M., Ta'eed V., Moss D., Eggleton B.J. Investigation of self-phase modulation based optical regeneration in single mode As_2Se_3 Chalcogenide glass fiber // Opt. Express. 2005. V.13. P. 7637-7641.

24. Guseinov G.D., Abdullayev G.B., Bidzinova S.N., Seidov F.M., Ismailov M.Z., Pashayev A.M., On new analogs of TlSe-type semiconductor compound // Phys. Letters . 1970. V. 7. № 7. P. 421-422.

25. Jackson S.D., Anzueto-Sánchez G. Chalcogenide glass Raman fiber laser // Appl. Phys. Lett., 2006. V.88. P. 221106.

26. Kolomiets B.T., Ryvkin S.M. photoelectric properties of indium sulfide and selenide // JTF. 1974.T. No. 19. S.2041-2046.

27. Petrusevich V.A., Sergeeva V.M. Optical and photoelectric properties of In_2Te_3 // FTT. 1960. No. 2. S.2858-2862.

28. Khvostenko A.S. Arsenic chalcogenides. An overview from the Physical and Chemical Properties of Solids series. - M., 1972. 93 p.

29. Najafov A.I., Alieva N.A., Khalilova K.G. Tellurium solubility in $TlGaTe_2$, $TlInTe_2$ crystals and electrophysical properties of solid solutions // Solid State Physics. 1918. V. 60. No. 9. P. 1658-1661.

30. Okhotin A.S., Pushkarsky N.S., Borovikova R.P., Smirnov R.A. Methods for studying the thermoelectric properties of semiconductors. Moscow: Atomizdat. 1969. 175 p.

31. Ahmedova C.A. Synthesis and investigation of glass formation and properties of obtained phases in the As_2S_3 - $TlInSe_2$ system // Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science No 87/2022. P. 12-17.